

Successful Completion of Sister Projects' Webinar Series on Gender Equality

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The AGRIGEP project, in collaboration with six Horizon Europe sister projects — GENDERSAFE, SUPPORTER, NEXUS, BUDGET IT, GENDERACTION+, and STREAM IT — successfully concluded a free monthly webinar series on gender equality in higher education and research institutions. The series, which ran from September 2024 to 20 May 2025, provided valuable insights and practical knowledge aimed at promoting gender equality and inclusivity across the academic sector. The AGRIGEP project coordinated the series, and each sister project hosted a webinar, mobilising their own network and sharing their experiences, best practices or even barriers they faced.

The webinars covered a broad range of timely and critical topics, many of which are at the forefront of the sister project activities. The webinar series featured the following eight topics:

- Effective Crisis Communication Management: Navigating Gender-Based Violence in Higher Education – hosted by GENDERSAFE
- Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement for GEP Implementation: Experiences from CEE Universities – hosted by AGRIGEP
- Embedding Inclusivity in Communication: The Power of Words and Visuals - hosted by SUPPORTER
- The Impact of Anti-Gender Discourses and Politics on Academic and Research Organisations- hosted by NEXUS
- Gender Budgeting: A Practical Application – hosted by BUDGET IT
- Relevance of Monitoring for Effective Gender Equality Policy Implementation in ERA - hosted by GenderAction +
- Advancing Gender Equality in STEAM Higher Education: Exploring Challenges, Opportunities, and Institutional Strategies - hosted by STREAM IT
- Revisiting AI Research and Teaching: Integrating Gender and Intersectional Perspectives - hosted by NEXUS

Each session attracted participants from diverse backgrounds, fostering rich discussions and the sharing of best practices. The series enabled institutions to learn from experts and peers, helping to strengthen their Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and policies.

The entire series was offered free of charge, with registration open to anyone interested in advancing gender equality in research and higher education.

For more information about the webinar recordings and related resources, please visit the AGRIGEP website at agrigeu.eu/ge-webinars.

About AGRIGEP

The **AGRIGEP project** (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01, Grant Agreement no. 101094158) supports structural change for gender equality in universities and research organisations in the field of agriculture and life sciences. Coordinated by the **Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)**, the project brings together the **Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU)** and the **University of Primorska (UP)** as widening institutions, supported by mentoring partners **Yellow Window**, Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC), and Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NaTE).

AGRIGEP Beneficiaries:

WIDENING PARTNERS

- Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE), **Coordinator**
- Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU)
- University of Primorska (UP)

MENTORING PARTNERS

- Yellow Window (YW)
- Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NATE)
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech (UPC)

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